

Article

Polyphenols Extracted from Grape Pomace as Synthesis Directing Agents of Photoactive ZnO: A Morphology and Reactivity Study

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Abstract

ZnO can be easily obtained using different salts as precursors, and many examples are present in the literature describing the effect of several additives in the synthesis. In this paper, we study the effects of the addition of polyphenols present in the residues of the wine supply chain. The polyphenols are extracted from grape pomace and fractionated, exploiting a membrane-based process equipped with polysulfone ultrafiltration membranes (cut-off 1 kDa and 5 kDa) that can separate the plethora of molecules into larger than 5 kDa and smaller than 1 kDa. The extract and its fractions after the ultrafiltration process were used as additives for the thermal precipitation synthesis of ZnO from Zn acetate. The chemical and physical properties were studied with the aim of understanding the characteristics that influence the activity of the photocatalysts. To this purpose, a commercial system was used for comparison, and the photoactivity was analyzed with a caffeine solution upon irradiation, exploiting the UVA and VIS electromagnetic radiation for the activation of the catalytic materials. The kind of polyphenol fraction affects the surface behaviors of the nanoparticles. Morphology, presence of trapped hole/electron centers, and acidity/basicity of the surface sites of ZnO appear to be the most relevant features in the efficiency towards caffeine degradation.

Keywords: polyphenols; extraction; membrane fractionation; green synthesis; ZnO; photocatalysis; caffeine degradation

Academic Editor: Jorge Bedia

Received: 31 January 2026

Revised: 25 March 2026

Accepted: 10 April 2026

Published: 16 April 2026

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1. Introduction

The European Commission's new policy guidelines for the 2024–2029 mandate place the circular economy at the heart of the transition to a sustainable and resilient economic model [1]. By promoting secondary materials and optimizing waste management, the aim is to extend the life of useful resources and reduce the environmental impact of production cycles [2]. A key aspect of the proposed actions is focused on critical raw materials, and more broadly, also the reuse of C-based materials that overburden the agro-industrial sector is another aspect to consider for decreasing the consumption of primary resources and promoting the reuse of wastes. The high availability of agro-industrial refuse makes their reuse appealing from two points of view: the presence of precious products present in the wastes and the prospect of eliminating at least part of those residues that accumulate and themselves become an environmental issue and a burden for society [3]. Agro-industrial wastes are a natural source of lignin, sugars, and polyphenols that can be adopted for a number of applications ranging from carbon-based materials production usable for the capture of contaminants in the gas and liquid phase [4] or for soil amendment and fertilization [5], nutraceutical and drug production [6,7]. In the regions of the world that have a temperate climate (and the Piedmont region in Italy is one of them), grape growing and wine production produce a large amount of grape pomace (GP), whose amount annually exceeds 10 Mt [8]. Due to its seasonality and polluting characteristics, the management and disposal of these large amounts of GP can pose a significant economic and environmental challenge. However, GP is one of the richest sources of natural phenolic compounds, which are widely studied due to their effective antioxidant and free radical scavenging activities, as biologically active substances in the food industry (nutraceuticals, food preservatives), in medicine, pharmacology, and biomedicine, as well as for many other industrial applications (natural colorants, cosmetics, etc.).

The research on the possible exploitation of GP for various purposes has been constantly growing during the last years, due to the increased general sensibility on issues like sustainability of agro-industrial production and the growing consumer demand for the use of natural versus synthetic compounds.

Like all material of plant origin, GP has a variable composition linked to the vintage, the cultivar, the winemaking technique (white or red winemaking), the duration of maceration, and the subsequent drying and storage conditions. This variability of composition concerns both the overall quantity (purity) and the nature of the extractable phenolic compounds and affects its final application [9].

Natural extracts are complex multicomponent systems whose functionality depends on molecular composition rather than extraction yield alone; therefore, extraction is commonly followed by fractionation to obtain compositionally tuned product streams and enable targeted valorization within circular biorefinery schemes [10].

Among scalable downstream strategies, membrane filtration enables simultaneous concentration and fractionation in a modular, pressure-driven process and is widely applied to polyphenol-rich extracts to separate low- and high-molecular-weight fractions [11–13]. Nanofiltration further allows efficient water recovery and internal solvent recycling, reducing energy demand and auxiliary chemical consumption [14,15].

Ultrafiltration and nanofiltration operate through molecular weight cut-off (MWCO)-controlled selective permeation, yielding retentates enriched in high-molecular-weight polyphenols and permeates enriched in smaller metabolites, and are characterized by mild operating conditions, scalability, and low chemical footprint, making them particularly compatible with green-extraction and circular-economy frameworks [16,17].

These aspects are all included in the Staff Exchange project “Phenocycles” (Exploiting the multifunctional properties of polyphenols: from wastes to high value products, Call

HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01, GA 101131420, www.phenocycles.unito.it (accessed on 9 April 2026)) funded by the European Commission, in which one of the main tasks is devoted to exploiting the polyphenols features (in particular the abundance of OH functional groups) to direct the synthesis of materials, in particular photoactive semiconductive nanoparticles modulating their photocatalytic behaviors as a function of particles size, structure, and morphology. Among all the photocatalysts known for their high activity (TiO_2 , WO_3 , CeO_2 , for instance), one of the most promising for the application in water depollution is zinc oxide (ZnO). It satisfies the requirement to be a well-known photocatalyst, widely characterized, and it can be considered a benchmark in materials science and photocatalysis, as it is the subject of several investigations. In fact, in recent years, the interest in this oxide has even overcome that in titania [18], also thanks to its accessibility, cost, and environmental compatibility [19].

ZnO is a semiconductor known for its excellent optical, electronic, and photocatalytic properties, making it an ideal candidate for the photocatalytic degradation of organic pollutants [20]. For what concerns, otherwise, possible substrates against which the ZnO can be directed, they belong to the category of Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs). They comprehend several commonly and widely used compounds not easily removed in the classical water treatment plants and destined to accumulate in the environment, in ground waters, and in the organisms living in and/or consuming that water. In this paper we focus the attention on the abatement of the stimulant caffeine ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$, CAF). Caffeine is the most widely used alkaloid; it acts as a central nervous system stimulant in humans [21,22] and is globally present in high concentrations in numerous natural species, such as coffee and cocoa beans, but also in several beverages and foods of anthropic production. Also, caffeine is a key compound in the pharmaceutical industry and is used in a wide range of medicines, as it is one of the world's leading psychostimulants, with an average global consumption of 70 mg/person/day [23]. Due to its widespread use, it is included in the U.S. EPA's list of high-volume chemical agents, and experts in various fields, including health professionals and environmentalists, are interested in the effects of caffeine on human health, including its possible involvement in chronic diseases such as cardiovascular disorders and cancer [23]. Numerous studies have highlighted its widespread presence in fresh and marine waters, demonstrating that wastewater treatment plants are unable to remove it completely. Caffeine concentrations in rivers range from 0.007 to 49.60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$, while in coastal marine areas they range from 0.045 to 0.33 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ [24–28].

Standing on all these aspects, ZnO , synthesized in the presence of polyphenols extracted from grape pomace and subsequently fractionated based on their molecular weights, has been tested in caffeine degradation, trying to assess a first attempt at correlation between the physico-chemical characteristics of the nanoparticles, induced by the use of the polyphenols and exploiting the chemical precipitation method, and their photoactivity.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Extraction and Fractionation of Polyphenols from Grape Pomace Matrix

Barbera Grape Pomace (GP) was sampled at the end of fermentative maceration, then was dried and milled. The extraction of polyphenols with ethanol:water (1:1) was performed according to a standardized green procedure [29] that allows for the complete recovery and reuse of ethanol that is itself a by-product of the wine industry. The dried extracts were stored freeze-dried and defrosted at room temperature when needed for the subsequent use. No modifications of the extracts original features are observed after freeze-drying/defrosting processes. GP extract was fractionated through a two-stage tangential-flow ultrafiltration (UF) cascade operating at the natural pH of the extract. The system, consisting of a recirculating feed tank, pumping unit, and polymeric UF modules, operated

in cross-flow configuration, collecting retentate in continuous recirculation and permeate in a graduated collector. Diafiltration was systematically applied at each UF step to prevent pore blocking and non-specific retention effects caused by high-MW species acting as dynamic barriers and interacting with low-MW polyphenols. Diafiltration consisted in partial permeate removal followed by replenishment with an equal volume of water, thus enhancing selective permeation and preventing indiscriminate retention. As described in Scheme 1, the extract was first processed through a 5 kDa UF membrane, yielding EUF5R (Retentate > 5 kDa, containing preferentially oligomeric/polymeric tannin-rich fraction) and a permeate. This latter was subsequently processed on a 1 kDa UF membrane, yielding EUFP (Permeate < 1 kDa, further refining the low-MW polyphenol fraction).

Scheme 1. The relevant steps of the ultrafiltration process applied to grape pomace. In this work, the Retentate > 5 kDa (EUF5R) and the Permeate < 1 kDa (EUFP) have been applied in the synthesis of ZnO photocatalysts.

Statistically significant compositional differences are observed between the raw extract and its fractions. Their composition is reported in Table 1 in terms of total polyphenol content (GAE), total condensed tannin content and their mean degree of polymerization (mDP), hydroxy cinnamyl tartaric acids (HCTA), flavonols, gallic acid, and flavan-3-ols ((+)-catechin, (−)-epicatechin, dimer B1), which represent the most important features to determine the characteristics of the natural extract.

Table 1. Polyphenolic composition of the raw extract and its fractions after the ultrafiltration process. All concentration values are expressed as mg/g d.w. dry extract. mDP (mean degree of polymerization) is a pure number.

	Raw Extract	Retentate 5 kDa (EUF5R)	Permeate 1 kDa (EUFP)
Total Polyphenols (GAE)	235 b *	378 a	90 c
Gallic acid	2.85 b	1.52 c	4.64 a
Total flavan-3-ols	5.53 b	4.62 c	6.25 a
Total HCTA	2.71 b	4.23 a	2.69 b
Total flavonols	8.33 a	7.40 b	3.98 c
Condensed tannins	62.8 b	107.7 a	7.9 c
mDP	3.5 a	3.7 a	2.3 b

* Different letters along the row discriminate the samples significantly different from one another ($p < 0.05$, Tukey's test).

Compared to the extract, the EUF5R fraction shows a concentration of higher MW molecules (total polyphenols, HCTA, condensed tannins) and, on the other side, a decrease in lower MW molecules (gallic acid, flavan-3-ols, flavonols). Conversely, the EUFP fraction shows a concentration in gallic acid and flavan-3-ols and a decrease in flavonols and condensed tannins. The mean Degree of Polymerization (mDP) parameter decreases significantly only for the EUFP fraction.

The overall process output showed a preferential composition into low-weight molecules and can be exemplified by the following percentual yields: EUF5R 22%, EUFP 63%, and a cumulative loss of approx. 10%. These two UF portions, being the most abundant, were used in the synthesis of ZnO materials, generating ZnO/EUF5R and ZnO/EUFP, respectively. Also, being the two fractions completely different in terms of molecular size, their exploitation as synthesis intermediates could envisage a possible mechanism through which the different families of polyphenols drive the first step of ZnO nucleation, affecting the final morphology and behaviors of the formed nanoparticles. For the sake of comparison and to verify the necessity of the ultrafiltration process for the synthesis of photoactive ZnO, the polyphenolic extract without separation was also applied in the synthesis of the ZnO/E sample.

2.2. Synthesis of ZnO Nanoparticles

ZnO samples were synthesized with and without polyphenolic additives following the procedure described in the Experimental section (Section 3.2.4). To evidence as well as possible the effects of the polyphenols molecular weight on the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles, only the retentate of the 5 kDa UF process (EUF5R, i.e., the largest molecules) and the permeate of the 1 kDa UF process (EUFP, i.e., the smallest molecules) were employed as coadjuvants in the synthesis. The color of the ZnO powders is expected to be completely white; nevertheless, all the powders appear grey, probably because of the presence of a small amount of metallic Zn or of carbonaceous residue formed by zinc acetate or organic matter reduction in the presence of reducing polyphenols, or because of the presence of small amounts of metals already present in the pomace and extracted together with the polyphenolic fraction. These metals would also be present in the fractionated extract as the UF membranes cannot hamper their passage. In order to evidence the origin of the grey color, ZnO powders were submitted to FTIR spectroscopic analysis (whose results are described in Section 2.3) and also digested using a mixture of HF and aqua regia, which was proved to be the best to induce the complete solubilization of the solids, and the digestate was analyzed by the ICP-OES method.

The results of the ICP-OES analysis are reported in Table 2. Apart from zinc, which was excluded by the list, potassium is present in higher concentration than other elements. This can be explained considering its large use in viticulture as a soil improver and fertilizer and the consequent presence in the grape pomace.

Table 2. Metal concentrations (mean \pm standard deviation) quantified by ICP-OES analysis on sample ZnO/E. The values are expressed as mg/kg. Zn was not included in the table.

Metal	Concentration (mg/kg)
Al	12 \pm 3
Ca	80 \pm 30
Cd	5 \pm 1
Cu	9 \pm 4
Fe	17 \pm 10
K	550 \pm 50
Mg	45 \pm 35
Na	80 \pm 60
Pb	43 \pm 4
Si	150 \pm 30

Among the other elements revealed, it seems important to evidence the presence of some transition metals that could act as dopants of ZnO affecting the catalytic behaviors

of the powders: this aspect will therefore be investigated considering the activity of the materials synthesized in the presence of the coadjuvants with that of the pure ZnO.

The discussion related to the physico-chemical features and photocatalytic behaviors of the synthesized materials will also include, in some cases, a comparison with the commercial ZnO/KADOX, which is pure, highly crystalline ZnO, whose extended characterization can be retrieved in ref. [30].

2.3. Characterization of ZnO Nanoparticles

The morphology of the synthesized ZnO particles is shown by FESEM images reported in Figure 1 and discussed considering the average particle size distribution values reported in Table 3. In general, all the particles present high aggregation and quite smooth surfaces without apparent defects, but their morphology changes depending on the experimental conditions applied.

The ZnO sample, obtained without any synthesis coadjuvant, is clearly different from the other samples, as it is made of acicular particles. To study in more detail how the additives affect the particles growth, Table 3 reports the average particle sizes considering two orthogonal directions that are the width and length of the particles in the case of acicular shape. ZnO/E presents an extended coalescence of the particles, but in the cauliflower-shaped blocks the spherical nanoparticles can still be recognized and measured to determine the size of the particles before the aggregation becomes coalescence.

Figure 1. Cont.

Figure 1. FESEM micrographs of ZnO nanoparticles: (a) ZnO, (b) ZnO/E, (c) ZnO/EUFP, (d) ZnO/EUF5R.

Table 3. Width and length of ZnO particles.

Samples	Width (nm)	Length (nm)
ZnO	76 ± 16	220 ± 64
ZnO/E	100 ± 23	114 ± 28
ZnO/EUFP	54 ± 10	75 ± 18
ZnO/EUF5R	69 ± 15	75 ± 25

The average width of ZnO particles is one-third with respect to the average length, whereas the addition of the extract, in particular in the case of ZnO/EUF5R, causes a decrease in the average length, which approaches the average width value, indicating the formation of more rounded nanoparticles. The size distribution curves reported in Figure S1 (length curves) allow for an explanation of the effect of extract addition in ZnO synthesis. The size distribution curves of the samples, whose synthesis was mediated by extracts, are less wide than that of the ZnO sample and centered at a lower value (114 nm). The decrease in this size can be easily explained considering that the effect of the polyphenolic extract in the synthesis is similar to the effect of other natural OH-containing compounds: the OH groups of the polyphenols act as complexing agents towards the Zn^{2+} ions of the precursor; the highly dispersed Zn^{2+} ions constitute many ZnO seeds that form, consequently, a lot of small ZnO particles. This effect is particularly visible for the samples obtained with EUFP and EUF5R: the particles result in both cases in highly dispersed and small sizes (75 nm as average), but the use of the smaller polyphenolic molecules, present in the EUFP fraction, seems to cause the formation of quite symmetrical spheric nanoparticles also highly uniform in size, suggesting a sort of tailoring effect on the particles growth. It can be hypothesized that the smaller polyphenolic compounds can easily surround the particles during their formation, hampering irregular growth and non-controlled coalescence, driving, therefore, the formation of almost spherical particles. A careful observation of the ZnO/EUF5R sample gives another cue for the discussion: the nanoparticles seem to be quite flat, forming in some part of the sample a sort of tower-like aggregates.

The XRD patterns for all ZnO samples (Figure 2) showed sharp peaks, indicating the formation of highly crystalline NPs and no amorphous phases. In this case, the dimension of the crystallites should correspond to the size of the particles. The Miller indices (100), (002), (101), (102), (110), (103), (200), (112), and (201) of the hexagonal wurtzite ZnO (JCPDS: 36-1451) were respectively assigned to the peaks corresponding to $2\theta \approx 31, 34, 36, 47, 56, 62, 66, 68, \text{ and } 69$. The reticular parameters of the nanoparticles are summarized in Table 4. The (0 0 2) and (1 0 0) peaks are utilized to calculate the lattice parameters c and

a using Equations (1) and (2), while volume (V) of the unit cell was calculated by using Equation (3). They were estimated using the following equations [31]:

$$\alpha = \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{3}\sin\theta} \quad (1)$$

$$c = \frac{\lambda}{\sin\theta} \quad (2)$$

$$V = 0.866a^2c \quad (3)$$

Scherrer's Equation (4) was also used to determine the crystallite size of the ZnO nanoparticles using the X-ray line broadening method. In the equation, D is the crystallite size, λ is the Cu K α radiation wavelength (1.5406 Å), K is the shape factor (0.9), β_{hkl} is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) in radians, and θ is the scattering angle.

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta_{hkl} \cos\theta} \quad (4)$$

Figure 2. XRD patterns of ZnO, ZnO/E, ZnO/EUFP, and ZnO/EUF5R in the range $2\theta = 20\text{--}80^\circ$ ((left) section) and $2\theta = 30\text{--}40^\circ$ ((right) section).

Table 4. Structural parameters of ZnO particles obtained by XRD measurements. The lattice parameters, the strain (ϵ), and the crystallite dimensions were evaluated by the Williamson-Hall (W-H) and Scherrer models.

Samples	Scherrer D (nm)	W-H D (nm)	ϵ (10^{-3})	a (Å)	c (Å)	V (Å ³)	I(002)/I(100)
ZnO	31	69	1.71	3.25	5.28	48.29	0.82
ZnO/E	34	91	2.31	3.25	5.28	48.27	0.83
ZnO/EUFP	32	85	1.36	3.25	5.29	48.44	0.75
ZnO/EUF5R	33	80	1.26	3.25	5.29	48.45	0.72

The hexagonal wurtzite crystal structure was confirmed for all the samples, also by the lattice parameters (Table 4). Indeed, a lattice volume (V) of about 48 Å³ was observed for all the samples, and no substantial differences were observed in the values of a and c , indicating the presence of extracts does not affect the elementary cell of ZnO.

The crystallite size and lattice deformation, which are two of the main factors controlling the broadening of diffraction peaks, were measured using both the Scherrer and the Williamson-Hall (W-H) model [32]. For Scherrer analysis, Equation (4) was utilised while for W-H crystallites and the associated intrinsic deformation, they were determined through the intercept and slope of the graph plotted with $\beta\cos\theta$ versus $4\sin\theta$.

The analysis results are shown in Table 4. It is observed that the D values obtained with the two methods are different. This result is not surprising, since a weakness of the Scherrer method is that it attributes only the contribution due to the crystallite size to the peak width, without taking into account the effects of lattice deformation and other types of crystalline defects that are instead taken into account in the W-H method, which provides a more accurate estimate of the crystallite size. Despite this, the same trend in D was observed for both methods.

Specifically, the size of the crystallites (D) seems to be influenced by the addition of the extract to the reaction solution. Interestingly, the highest D value is shown by the ZnO/E sample (i.e., 34 and 91 nm for Scherrer and W-H methods, respectively), which is the one formed by coalescent particles, indicating the coalescence brought an extension of crystallinity. ZnO shows a D value of 69 nm, which is the lowest value observed. No substantial differences were observed in the crystallite size obtained for the samples prepared with the fractionated extracts. Both samples, in fact, showed a D (by the W-H method) of approximately 80 nm, which is an intermediate value between that observed for the ZnO/E sample and the ZnO synthesized without extract.

Also the strain values (ϵ), reported in Table 4, suggest some interesting features of the systems. Strain is a critical parameter that can also affect the structural integrity of materials. It refers to deformation within a material due to the effect of lattice defects and external forces, which affect the material strength and, consequently, the overall stability of the particles [33]. In Table 4, the highest strain values are observed for the ZnO/E sample (coalescent crystallites) and for ZnO (non-spherical nanoparticles), whereas a lower strain value is reported for ZnO/EUF5R and ZnO/EUFP, for which the evaluation of the W-H D values reflects the real size observed in FESEM images (about 80 nm vs. 75 nm, from the two techniques, respectively).

Table 4 also reports 002/100 signal intensity ratios of sample diffractograms. This parameter allows highlighting the difference in the relative intensities of the two signals: when the value increases, preferential crystallite growth on the c-axis occurs [34]. ZnO and ZnO/E show similar values of 0.72, whereas ZnO/EUFP and ZnO/EUF5R show lower values of 0.75 and 0.72, respectively.

Considering the spherical shape of ZnO/EUFP particles, the value of 0.75 could be considered as a reference for symmetric particles; therefore, values larger than 0.75 should correspond to particles elongated along the c-axis, whereas values lower than 0.75 should correspond to flat particles growing along the a and b-axes. The hypothesis seems to be confirmed by the FESEM results: ZnO (002/100 ratio = 0.82) is made of elongated particles with a preferential growth along the c-axis; ZnO/EUF5R (002/100 ratio = 0.72) is made of flat particles with a limited growth along the c-axis. The situation of the ZnO/E sample is quite odd, as it shows a 002/100 ratio of 0.83, but the morphology of the system observed in the FESEM image is not directly comparable with a specific particle shape; nevertheless, the value seems to suggest the coalescence occurs among elongated particles.

The band gap of the representative materials was analyzed by applying the Tauc plot method to the UV-VIS-NIR diffuse reflectance spectra. The details of the elaborations are reported in the SI Section (Figures S2 and S3). Table 5 reports the band gap values of the samples investigated in this paper compared with the value of the commercially available ZnO/KADOX sample, which is reported to be pure, highly crystalline, and non-defective.

Table 5. Optical band gap energy (E_g) obtained using the Tauc plot on representative samples compared with commercial ZnO/KADOX.

Sample	E_g (eV)
ZnO	3.23
ZnO/E	3.24
ZnO/EUFP	3.23
ZnO/KADOX	3.26

The obtained E_g values are consistent with those found in the literature [30]. Only minor variations among the samples were observed, indicating that the addition of the polyphenolic extract and its filtered fractions does not significantly modify the optical band gap of ZnO; nevertheless, all the values are significantly slightly different from the ZnO/KADOX one, as expected for systems that are more defective than the commercial sample.

The adsorption/desorption of nitrogen at 77 K reported in Figure 3 allowed for evidence of the textural features of the materials. All the isotherms show a trend typical of mesoporous materials (Type IV of the IUPAC classification), and all the materials possess almost the same specific surface area except ZnO/EUF5R, which shows an area slightly higher than the other samples (Table 6). The comparison with the particles morphology evidenced by FESEM measurements evidences the important limit of N_2 adsorption measurements: the highly aggregated samples do not show in a realistic way the area exposed by the single particles but only the area of the aggregates. The higher the aggregation, the lower the area, even if the single particle size decreases.

Figure 3. N_2 isotherms at 77 K. The curves have been shifted for a better observation of the hysteresis loops.**Table 6.** BET specific surface area and BJH desorption mesopore volume of ZnO samples.

Sample	BET Specific Surface Area (m^2/g)	BJH Desorption Mesopores Volume (cm^3/g)
ZnO	7.5 ± 0.3	0.04
ZnO/E	7.4 ± 0.3	0.04
ZnO/EUFP	7.8 ± 0.3	0.11
ZnO/EUF5R	8.5 ± 0.4	0.11

From the mesoporosity point of view (the results are reported in Figure 4 and Table 6), the BJH model reveals the presence of two families of mesopores: smaller than 15 nm and larger than 15 nm. Considering the size of the particles obtained by FESEM investigation (50 nm or larger), only the pores smaller than 15 nm could be intraparticle, even if FESEM images do not reveal surface roughness or void spaces that can be recognized as pores; therefore, the presence of internal porosity cannot be proven by this technique. Otherwise, the pores larger than 15 nm are surely compatible with the void space formed by particle aggregation and can be defined as interparticle. The addition of the extract in the synthesis tends to decrease the number of small mesopores, giving denser particles, whereas the number of large mesopores increases, probably due to a non-efficient packing of the small particles in the aggregated powders. The effect is particularly evident when the ultrafiltered extracts are added to the ZnO precursors, independently of the membrane used for the filtration: the smaller pores decrease, the larger pores increase, and the total pore volume increases from 0.04 to 0.11 cm³/g.

Figure 4. BJH desorption pore size distribution curves.

EPR was used to compare the defectivity of the synthesized samples with that of the commercial pure and highly crystalline ZnO/KADOX but also to individuate other paramagnetic contaminants eventually present in the ZnO structure (Figure 5). The intensity of the signals was modified in order to better visualize the spectra.

The benchmark sample ZnO/KADOX shows the typical spectrum already described in the literature [30], indicating the presence of trapped electron centers (Zn⁺, signal at $g = 1.96$), trapped hole centers (O⁻, $g = 2.014$), and free electrons (at $g = 2.0023$). None of the other materials under study show the presence of O⁻ sites. In addition, ZnO and ZnO/E contain Zn⁺ sites evidenced by the g signal at 1.96 and free electrons ($g = 2.0023$), and ZnO/EUFP only contains free electrons. All signals are, contrarily to those observed for ZnO/KADOX, very intense. No additional peaks are observed, and that allows to exclude the presence of paramagnetic impurities.

In conclusion, EPR spectra suggest that oxygen and zinc ions behave differently in different samples. As these sites can affect the photoactivity of the materials, in particular if they are at the interface of solids/environment, FTIR spectroscopy was chosen as an additional physico-chemical characterization technique, as it can reveal the presence of functional groups providing some information at the level of the materials surface. Figure 6

reports the spectra of ZnO representative samples compared with the ZnO/KADOX in the 4000–1000 cm^{-1} range. The profile of the curves is typical of powdery materials, with a very important absorption at low wavenumbers (below 1100 cm^{-1}) due to the vibrations of ZnO bulk. In the rest of the spectra, it is possible to recognize: (i) the OH stretching vibrations related to surface OH groups interacting via hydrogen bonding in the region 4000–2500 cm^{-1} and representing the hydrated layer at the surface of the materials exposed to the air; (ii) some weak CH stretching signals below 3000 cm^{-1} due to organic contaminants always visible in powdery materials; (iii) a quite intense signal at 2345 cm^{-1} visible in all the spectra except for the ZnO/KADOX sample; and (iv) some not well-defined and quite weak absorptions in the range 2000–1000 cm^{-1} which become a strong and multi-component group of bands for the ZnO/KADOX sample. These two last absorptions deserve an in-depth discussion, as they can be correlated with the behaviors of oxygen and zinc ions at the surface of the solid materials. In fact, atmospheric CO_2 molecules can interact with ZnO surfaces in two ways: they can be linearly adsorbed on Zn cations, giving a signal at 2345 cm^{-1} , witnessing the presence of Lewis acid sites, and they can interact in the bent form with oxygen anions, forming the so-called carbonate-like groups responsible for a complex signal in the 2000–1000 cm^{-1} range in the FTIR spectrum, witnessing the presence of basic sites. Interestingly, all the ZnO samples synthesized via the precipitation method and investigated in this study mainly produce signals at 2345 cm^{-1} , indicating that these oxides are mainly acidic, whereas ZnO/KADOX mainly forms the low-frequency signals, indicating that ZnO/KADOX is mainly basic. The different surface basicity/acidity is expected to affect the photoactivity of the materials that will be described in Section 2.4.

Figure 5. 77 K EPR spectra of some representative materials compared with commercial ZnO/KADOX. The numbers indicate the amplification factor applied to better visualize the differences among the spectra.

Figure 6. FTIR spectra of powders dispersed in KBr. The curves have been vertically shifted for the sake of clarity. Also, the main signals and their attribution are evidenced in the Figure.

2.4. Caffeine Degradation

The photocatalytic performances of the synthesized materials were evaluated through caffeine degradation (5.0 mg/L) under simulated solar irradiation. The evolution of C/C_0 is reported in Figure 7, and the apparent kinetic constants are summarized in Table 7. Control experiments performed in the dark showed no caffeine removal, confirming that degradation is entirely photo-induced.

Figure 7. Caffeine abatement upon irradiation time (ZnO catalysts concentration 0.2 g/L; caffeine initial concentration 5.0 mg/L) obtained for ZnO/EUF5R (green triangles), ZnO (black squares), ZnO/EUFP (blue triangles), ZnO/E (red circles), and commercial ZnO/KADOX (black diamonds, dashed line).

Table 7. Apparent rate constants of ZnO photocatalysts.

Sample	kapp (min ⁻¹)	R ²
ZnO	0.02185	0.9987
ZnO/E	0.01563	0.9989
ZnO/EUFP	0.0154	0.9616
ZnO/EUF5R	0.0541	0.9894

Under the adopted conditions (low substrate concentration and constant catalyst loading), the degradation profiles follow an apparent pseudo-first-order kinetic model, consistent with the Langmuir–Hinshelwood approximation commonly applied in heterogeneous photocatalysis [35]. The corresponding apparent rate constants (kapp) were obtained from linear regression of $-\ln(C_0/C)$ versus irradiation time as shown in the Supporting Information (Figure S4, Table S1).

ZnO/EUF5R exhibited the highest activity (kapp = 0.055 min⁻¹), achieving complete caffeine removal within ~100 min. Pristine ZnO showed intermediate performance (kapp = 0.030 min⁻¹), while ZnO/E and ZnO/EUFP displayed lower degradation rates (0.015 and 0.016 min⁻¹, respectively). Despite these interesting results, all samples show a photoactivity more limited than the commercial ZnO/KADOX. Cyclic degradation tests were carried out without separating the photocatalyst from the reaction suspension. After each irradiation cycle, caffeine was added to restore the initial concentration (5 ppm), and the suspension was reused under identical experimental conditions, thus avoiding additional handling of the catalyst [35].

The results obtained for ZnO/EUFP reused over two cycles indicate that the material is stable and reusable at least under the examined conditions, as it can be seen in Figure S5.

An additional insight into the reaction mechanism followed by the photocatalysts was obtained by applying EPR measurements in the presence of DMPO spin trap, useful to evidence the formation of OH and O₂⁻ radicals expected to be formed by ZnO during the irradiation [36]. Figure 8 shows the signals (section A) and the histogram of related intensity (section B) of the representative samples compared with commercial ZnO/KADOX.

All spectra evidence the typical signal of DMPO-OH adduct due to OH radical formation. The formation of this strongly reacting species allows us to hypothesize that the removal of the organic molecule is actually due to its mineralization, as reported in the literature for similar systems. The signal produced by the ZnO/KADOX sample is much more intense than the others after 25 min of total irradiation time, but it decreases fast with time, whereas the other materials show the opposite trend, producing a weak signal that increases along irradiation time.

In conclusion, these results indicate that the presence of polyphenolic additives in the ZnO synthesis does not automatically enhance photocatalytic activity; rather, the molecular characteristics of the synthesis directing agents determine the final material performance. The different behaviors can be discussed considering structural, morphological, and surface features.

FESEM images (Figure 1) show pronounced coalescence for ZnO/E although BET surface areas are similar for all samples (Table 6). Actually, nitrogen adsorption reflects the feature of aggregated powders at the solid phase and may not represent the real dispersion state in suspension. Standing by this conclusion, the specific surface area does not represent a feature to discuss when dealing with the photocatalytic activity of the materials.

The limited reactivity observed for ZnO/EUFP, similar to that of ZnO/E, cannot be explained in terms of particle aggregation, as they appear well dispersed in the FESEM images. Instead, it could be attributed to the absence of free electrons and oxygen, as revealed by the EPR results.

Figure 8. (A) EPR spectra of representative samples compared with commercial ZnO/KADOX obtained in the presence of DMPO spin trap and registered after a total irradiation time of 25 min (20 min before the DMPO addition and 5 min after). (B) intensity of the signals.

The good reactivity of ZnO/KADOX, significantly more efficient than the nanoparticles synthesized in the present work, is likely due to the presence of trapped electron centers, trapped hole centers, and free electrons, and FTIR results suggest that the paramagnetic features also reflect some peculiar chemistry at the surface of the materials. The interaction of the solids with atmospheric gaseous CO₂ evidences that all synthesized ZnO expose Lewis acid sites at their surface (i.e., zinc cations) and almost no basicity, whereas ZnO/KADOX only shows a strong surface basicity (brought by oxygen anions). Although the presence of surface carbonate-like species should limit the contact between the material and caffeine, slowing down or even hampering the photoactivity of ZnO/KADOX, this is not observed; therefore, the oxygen basic sites are expected to have an important role in the photocatalysis induced by ZnO.

Even if the presence of trace metals revealed by analysis ICP-OES (Table 2) could suggest a non-negligible effect on ZnO photocatalytic effect, all the analyses carried out do not allow reaching a definitive conclusion regarding a possible surface doping effect, but it is worth highlighting that the best photocatalytic system (ZnO/KADOX) is known to be made of pure, non-defective, and highly crystalline zinc oxide.

Overall, the results indicate that the high-molecular-weight polyphenolic fraction (EUF5R) acts as an effective morphology-directing agent, generating a ZnO nanostructure that favors photocatalytic degradation under the investigated conditions. The interpretation is therefore framed as a structure–activity correlation, while more detailed mechanistic insights would require dedicated surface and charge-carrier analyses.

Morphological anisotropy also appears relevant. The I(002)/I(100) ratios derived from XRD (Table 4) suggest preferential growth differences among samples, indicating variations in exposed crystallographic facets. Such differences may influence surface reactivity and charge carrier dynamics. ZnO/EUF5R combines reduced aggregation with modified crystal growth, which plausibly contributes to its enhanced performance.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Materials for Synthesis

The materials used included zinc acetate dehydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99%, (Acros organics—Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA)), pure ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}$, Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany).

All chemical reagents used in the experiments or in the synthesis were of analytical grade and were used as received.

3.2. Methods

3.2.1. Preparation of Grape Pomace Extracts

Barbera Grape Pomace (GP) was sampled at the end of fermentative maceration and then was dried and milled. The extraction of polyphenols with ethanol:water (1:1) was performed according to a standardized green procedure [29] that allows for the complete recovery and reuse of the solvent; moreover, ethanol itself is a byproduct of the wine industry. The extracts were deprived of alcohol under vacuum, then freeze-dried.

3.2.2. Ultra Filtration Process

The system, composed of a pilot skid (PB100, Hydro Air Research Srl, Lodi, Italy), was equipped with different polysulfone membranes: 5 kDa (SDR5-1812, filter area 0.33 m^2) and 1 kDa (SDR10-1812, filter area 0.33 m^2). A pressure of 4 bar for all separation steps was exploited. UF experiments were conducted at the natural pH of the extract and in tangential mode, i.e., with the sample feed flow tangentially to the membrane surface. The retentate was continuously recirculated in the feed tank, while the permeate was collected in a graduated cylinder, monitoring its flow and permeation rate. Every filtration step adopted a diafiltration to enhance the separation, consisting of partial permeate removal followed by replenishment with an equal volume of water. The experimental set-up was the following: the extract (14 g) was solubilized into 2 L of deionized water, and the resulting solution was clarified by means of centrifugation (4200 rpm, 15 min). The mixture was processed on the 5 kDa membrane, recovering an overall amount of 0.4 L of retentate (EUF5R) and 2.8 L of permeate, after diafiltration. A sample of the latter (2.65 L) was immediately destined for a 1 kDa membrane. At the end of the process, an overall amount of 0.5 L of retentate and 4.3 L of permeate (EUF6) was obtained after diafiltration. Each fractionation stream was sampled and freeze-dried.

3.2.3. Characterization of Polyphenolic Extracts

The polyphenolic characterization of the extract and its fractions was as follows: The total polyphenol content (GAE) was determined with spectrophotometric methods [10]. The total condensed tannin content and their mean degree of polymerization (mDP) were determined with the phloroglucinolysis HPLC method [37]. Hydroxy cinnamyl tartaric

acids (HCTA) were determined by HPLC according to [38]. Flavonols were determined using the same chromatographic conditions and sample preparation as HCTA but with the signal monitored at 360 nm. Gallic acid and flavan-3-ols—(+)-catechin, (–)-epicatechin, dimer B1—were determined by HPLC using a method for seed analysis modified for wine. All analyses were performed in duplicate. The data were processed with univariate (one-way ANOVA and Tukey's test) analysis techniques [39].

3.2.4. ZnO Synthesis

The grape pomace extracts were used in three ways: directly as they are, after ultrafiltration on a polysulphone membrane with a cut-off of 1 kDa, and after ultrafiltration through a membrane with a cut-off of 5 kDa. The extract (E), ultrafiltrate permeate < 1 kDa (EUFP), and ultrafiltrate retentate 5 kDa (EUF5R) (0.105 g) were dissolved in 120 mL of water at room temperature and stirred at room temperature for 2 h in a crucible. Next, 6.42 g of zinc acetate dihydrate [$\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$] were added, and the mixture was stirred for a further hour. The pH was 6. The solutions were then heated to 90 °C to form a paste-like solution inside the crucible. The samples were then calcined in a muffle furnace (in air, at 500 °C for 2 h) to finalize the synthesis and obtain stable zinc oxide products. The same procedure was also applied without extract addition in order to evidence the ZnO modification brought by the extract addition. The resulting materials were named ZnO/E, ZnO/EUFP, ZnO/EUF5R, and ZnO, respectively. Commercial ZnO/KADOX from Sigma-Aldrich was considered for the sake of comparison.

3.2.5. Characterization of ZnO-NPs

ZnO/E digestate powders were digested in a microwave oven (Milestone-MEGA 1200), and their element content was determined by ICP-OES measurements. A mixture of HF (1 mL) and aqua regia (5 mL) in 100 mL tetrafluoromethoxyl vessels was added to 100 mg of the material. The digestion program was as follows: 5 min at 250 W, 5 min at 400 W, 5 min at 600 W, 5 min at 250 W, and finally 30 min of ventilation. The resulting solutions were filtered through cellulose filters with a pore size of 0.45 µm (Whatman grade 5) and diluted to 10 mL with ultrapure water (Milli-Q (Millipore), resistivity = 18.2 MΩ·cm). The elemental content of the digested samples was determined using Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy, ICP-OES (PerkinElmer, model Optima 7000 DV), equipped with a cross-flow nebulizer, a Scott spray chamber, an alumina injector, and an Echelle monochromator. The radiofrequency power applied was 1300 W. Plasma, auxiliary, and nebulizer gas flows were 15, 0.2, and 0.6 L min⁻¹, respectively. The signals were measured in triplicate. Calibration was performed using external standard solutions prepared from standard reference solutions.

A field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM TESCAN S9000G, Brno, Czech Republic) was used to examine the particle morphology. Before FESEM analysis, samples were coated with a 5 nm thick layer of Cr. Using the program ImageJ® version 1.54s10 (U.S. National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MD, 20892, USA), the mean particle size of at least 100 particles was determined from FESEM images. From these data, the distribution was obtained.

The crystalline structure was evaluated by the X-ray diffraction technique using an X-ray diffractometer (XRD) Malvern Panalytical X'Pert Pro (Malvern, Panalytical B.V., Almelo, The Netherlands) equipped with an X'Celerator detector using Cu Kα radiation generated at 45 kV and 40 mA within a 2θ range of 20–80°.

UV-Vis Diffuse Reflectance spectra were collected in the range 200–800 nm using a Perkin Elmer Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer, Inc., Waltham, MA,

USA) equipped with an integrating sphere and elaborated via the Tauc-plot method. A Teflon sample with 100% reflectance was used as a reference.

The nitrogen gas volumetric adsorption measurement at 77 K recorded with an ASAP 2020 Micrometrics instrument (Norcross, GA 30093, USA) was used to determine the BET specific surface area and pore volume (samples were outgassed overnight at 100 °C to remove the adsorbed atmospheric gases from the surface and pores prior to the analyses).

EPR spectra of the powders (about 50 mg) were recorded at 77 K in an X-band Bruker EMX instrument (Bruker, Billerica, MA, USA) equipped with a cylindrical cavity operating at 100 kHz field modulation (microwave frequency 9.86/9.54 GHz, microwave power 5/20 mW, modulation amplitude 1 Gauss).

FTIR spectroscopy was carried out on the Equinox 55 by Bruker (Bruker Optik GmbH, Ettlingen, Germany), equipped with a Globar source and DTGS detector. The spectra were obtained by collecting 128 scans with resolution 4 cm⁻¹ in transmission mode on KBr pellets containing the dispersed powders.

3.2.6. Photodegradation Tests and Caffeine HPLC Analysis

Photodegradation experiments were conducted using caffeine as a model target pollutant. 10 mg of the ZnO catalysts were inserted in a 50 mL volumetric flask that was then filled using a 5 mg/L caffeine solution prepared beforehand. The suspensions were sonicated for 5 min, transferred in closed Pyrex cells, and placed in a solarbox (CO.FO.ME.GRA S.r.l., Milan, Italy) equipped with a 1500 W Xenon lamp and a 340 nm cut-off filter. The irradiance of the lamp, measured with a UV-Multimeter system, was 26.7 W/m². The temperature inside the solarbox was around 40 °C and the initial pH of the suspension was around 8 with marginal variation between materials. Total irradiation time was 5 h for each experiment, and suspensions were maintained under magnetic stirring for the whole duration of the tests. The collected samples were filtered using 0.22 µm syringe filters to remove catalyst particles before analysis.

Control tests of the same duration (5 h) were performed in dark conditions by wrapping the cells in aluminum foil and placing them in the solarbox to ensure that the same temperature and stirring conditions were applied. Cyclic degradation tests were carried out without separating the photocatalyst from the reaction suspension. After each irradiation cycle, caffeine was added to restore the initial concentration (5 ppm). Caffeine concentration was monitored by HPLC, using a Merck-Hitachi instrument (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) equipped with a Lichrospher RP-C18 (125 mm × 4 mm) column. Elution was performed isocratically using 85% water (acidified using 0.1% phosphoric acid) and 15% ACN with a flow of 0.8 mL/min. Caffeine detection was performed using a UV detector at 275 nm. All measurements were conducted in triplicate.

EPR was also used to evidence the formation of reactive oxygenated species at RT in the same instrumental conditions described above. A volume of 1 mL of 0.2 g/L suspension in water of each sample was irradiated in Solarbox for 20 min, then 2 µL of DMPO 17 mM was added to the mixture and left under irradiation for a further 5 min (total irradiation time of 25 min) before recording the spectrum. Another spectrum was also recorded after a total irradiation time of 35 min (20 before and 15 after DMPO addition).

4. Conclusions

Residual biomasses can be recovered and submitted to the extraction of polyphenolic compounds in a valorization optic in order to apply the circular economy approach and decrease the mass of the refuse, also opening the way to technological processes of interest for society. The extraction of polyphenolic substances represents *per se* an advantage for society, as most costly processes for the synthesis of such substances can be avoided, but

the separation of grape pomace extracts in fractions of different molecular weights can represent an additional advantage, as the fractionated substances can be more appropriately applied in different processes.

In this study we evaluated the polyphenol-driven synthesis of photoactive ZnO in order to (a) extract and reuse the polyphenols from residual biomasses for (b) obtaining a photoactive material useful for CECs polluted water decontamination.

The characterization of the obtained ZnO suggests important reflection points to correlate the photoactivity of the oxide to specific physico-chemical behaviors. Once this step is completed and it is ascertained that some correlations exist, future work will deepen the study in order to exactly determine the features to take into account for designing the optimal material and process.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/catal16040360/s1>, Figure S1: Particles length distribution curves of ZnO, ZnO/E, ZnO/EUFP and ZnO/EUF5R. The term “length” indicates that the longer side was measured in case of acicular particles; Figure S2: Reflectance spectra (R%) as a function of wavelength (λ , 200–800 nm) for ZnO (black), ZnO/E (red), ZnO/EUFP (yellow) and ZnO/KADOX (green); Figure S3: Additional image to support the data obtained. Representation of the Tauc plot with the corresponding equations of the extrapolated straight lines for the ZnO, ZnO/E, ZnO/EUFP and ZnO/KADOX samples; Figure S4: Pseudo-first-order kinetic plots for the photocatalytic degradation of caffeine (initial concentration 5 mg/L) for the different catalysts; Figure S5: Photocatalytic abatement of caffeine (initial concentration 5 mg/L) obtained using ZnO/EUFP over two cycles performed with the same material; Table S1: Numerical values obtained for the linear fits of the pseudo-first-order kinetic plots presented in Figure S4.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, G.M. and G.G.d.C.; methodology, G.M., G.G.d.C., G.G., S.T., M.G., S.M., A.B., M.D.M. and E.L.; investigation, M.D.M., A.B., M.M., C.F., S.V., D.P., G.G., M.G. and L.B.; data curation, G.M., G.G.d.C., M.D.M., M.M., G.G., S.T., M.G.F., M.G., S.M., E.L., L.B. and A.B.; writing—original draft preparation, G.M., G.G.d.C., M.D.M., M.M., D.P., A.B.P., G.G., S.T. and M.G.; writing—review and editing, G.M. and G.G.d.C.; visualization, G.M. and G.G.d.C.; Funding Acquisition: G.M., G.G.d.C. and M.G. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This work was funded by PHENOCYCLES project funded by the European Union under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Staff Exchanges. Grant agreement ID: 101131420 (DOI: 10.3030/101131420).

Data Availability Statement: Data will be available on request.

Acknowledgments: The authors acknowledge support from Project CH4.0 under the MUR (Italian Ministry for Universities and Research) program “Dipartimenti di Eccellenza 2023–2027” (CUP: D13C22003520001).

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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